

Environmental safety of bulk-loaded dust-forming cargos transportation by water and possible directions of its improvement

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Abstract

The results of theoretical studies on possible directions of improving environmental safety at various stages of the transportation of bulk dusty cargoes by water are presented. It is shown that at the stage of performing transshipment operations (loading / unloading), possible directions for increasing the environmental safety of handling bulk dust products are: ensuring sanitary and hygienic conditions during the transshipment process; improvement of equipment and technology for performing reloading operations (organizational methods, technical and technological measures); urban planning activities. At the stage of transportation of bulk dusty cargoes by water, the use of special containers, the use of cargo sealing materials, the formation of a protective film on the surface of the dusty cargo, the screening of the dusty cargo surface with highly concentrated suspensions in the form of pastes.

Keywords: Bulk-loaded dust-forming cargo, Transportation, Environmental safety, Improvement directions.

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1. Introduction

In many industrial processes due to the peculiarities of their technological features, production methods, raw materials nature and intermediate and finished products, the dust formation is going on polluting the air of the premises, the working zones and the surrounding area. The economic facilities affected with the dust emission problem include the waterborne transport (WT) performing the transportation of the bulk-loaded dust-forming cargos (BDC). The transportation comes with the emissions of solid aerosols (dust) into the atmosphere followed by the environmental pollution not only on the transportation route but also on the port territory and adjacent areas including both land territory and water basin. By the nature of their action on a human organism, the dust particles – when inhaled – can cause diseases of the respiratory system at the level of the bronchi and pneumoconiosis at the level of the lungs. The hazard having the highest priority comes from the particles less than $5\mu\text{cm}$ by size as they penetrate into the deep layers of the lung tissue. Researches on this pressing matter of the day are conducted quite extensively; however, as for WT, until now, this issue is considered mainly only for the stage of the loading/unloading operations.

In these conditions, quite clear is the urgent need to analyze the environment dustiness extent on the waterways, in the ports and the surrounding areas occurred as the result of the BDC transportation. Also it is necessary to identify the main causes and sources of the dust formation, which would become the basis for the development of possible directions of the environmental safety (ES) improvement at the BDC transportation.

2. Development

This article is aimed at a theoretical framework development of the environmental safety of the BDC transportation by water and its possible improvement directions outlining.

In accordance with the Federal Law on the protection of the environment, ES is understood as the state of protection of the natural environment and vital human interests from the possible negative impacts of economic and other human activities, natural and technological disasters and their consequences. In the similar ways, under ES of BDC transportation, it is

proposed to understand such state of the BDC transportation, which ensures the protection of both the environment and the population against the forming dust on the required level of standards.

It is widely accepted to divide all the cargos transported by water into three groups: bulk goods, general commodities (breakbulk goods) and ones required maximum security.

The bulk cargos include bulk-loaded loose goods, hereunder referred to as BLC; the latter cargo kind makes the subject of the current research. According to the sphere of their use, BLC are divided into the following categories: construction materials (cement, sand, gravel, expanded clay, rubble stone and earth), food products (grain, flour, compound animal feedstuff), fuels (coal) and chemical goods (mineral fertilizers, caustic soda ash).

Based on the fractions sizes and shapes, BLC are divided into dusty ones (sand, cement, flour, coal), granular stuff (fertilizer, grain) and lumps (coal, stone). BLC are characterized by specifications of their composite particles and among them size, weight, density, humidity, natural temperature, coefficient of friction, bulk density, environmental safety and storage conditions needed to be considered for their transportation.

For the transportation of the bulk-loaded cargos by water, the special vessels are used such as the bulkers and dry bulk carriers.

The procedure of transportation of the bulk-loaded cargo is regulated by the following main international and domestic guidelines:

- SOLAS (International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea), chapter 74, part VI;
- International Maritime Code for solid bulk-loaded cargos;
- Code of safe practice for cargo stowage and securing;
- The Code of Practice for the Safe Loading and Unloading of Bulk Carriers;
- Manual on Loading/Unloading of Solid Bulk Cargos for Terminal Personnel Members;
- RD 31.11.01-92 Regulations for safe maritime transportation of non-grain bulk-loaded cargos (NNG regulations) in 2

volumes (with alterations made in 1994-1997);

- Regulations for safety of cargos maritime transportation, RD 31.11.21.16-2003;
- Terms of carriage requirements (TCR) for each ship;
- Standard loading plan (SLP).

Both maritime and river transportation processes consist of cargos transportation by ships <departure port - destination port> and cargos loading/unloading in the ports from one vehicles to other, i.e. from water vehicles to land vehicles and vice versa as well as from water vehicles of one type to that of another type. In accordance with these process types, the technology of the maritime and river transportation process consists of two components: technology of transportation and technology of transshipment [1]. In addition, some ports can store cargos in warehouses before they are sent to their destination port.

The transportation technology refers to the ways of cargos placement & securing on ships and the system of actions performed on a ship before and during its voyage for the prevention of the cargos deterioration and damage. For implementation of a specific transportation technology, the latter requires using certain technical means.

The technology of port transshipment operations is understood as the nature and the sequence of the cargo manipulations when it is moved from one vehicle to another, no matter through the warehouse or bypassing it. Each specific technology of transshipment operations involves the use of certain technical means. Any cargos relocation in the port during the technological processes implementation can be made in a number of variants, for example:

<warehouse-ship-transportation-warehouse>;

<car-ship-transportation-warehouse>;

<one ship - another ship - transportation - warehouse>.

During the technological processes implementation, the cargos moving inside of the port can be made in different ways, for example:

<warehouse-ship-transportation-warehouse>;

<train-ship-transportation-warehouse>;

<ship-ship-transportation-warehouse>.

To perform each of the components of the BDC transportation stage, involved are ships, mechanisms, instruments, equipment, materials and service personnel. To a certain extent, even the use of the listed components in their intended purpose leads to a pollution of the environment.

For example, moving of a cargo within the port territory is carried out with the use of this or that mobile equipment running on the traditional fuel – this leads to the environment pollution with exhaust gases.

The transshipment equipment maintenance and repair is carried out in special workshops and at sites where oily and waste water, exhaust gases, industrial debris are formed, which are the sources of the port water area, soil and atmosphere pollution.

Also the personnel members of the transshipping operations contribute to the pollution source as their living needs satisfaction (dining rooms, showers, bathrooms) results in the formation of the sewage and household garbage causing the port environment contamination.

In these conditions, in order to maintain the normal environmental situation, both within the port and outside of it, on the routes of transportation and in the port-adjacent territories, it is necessary to know the specifications of reloaded cargos, the used types of vehicles, technological equipment units & complexes and the technology of reloading processes. All this data should be evaluated from the point of view of the possible formation of these or that adverse environmental factors for the nature and humans. Based on this data, – the development is possible of the adequate measures able to reduce the negative impact of the transportation process on the environment, both on the transportation water routes and in the port itself including its surrounding area.

The cargos BDC being the subject of the present research are transported without containers, in bulk. They consist of a large number of homogeneous particles or particles of different size; such cargos are coal, ore, alumina, chemical cargos, fertilizers, building materials, etc. The main important for the water transportation BDC specifications are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Shipping specifications of BDC transported by water

Name of goods	MPS (mm)	Permissible humidity	< > (mm)	Slumping
Coal	0.040	0.060	-	Yes
Apatite concentrate	0.102	0.061	1.5	
Nepheline concentrate	0.020	0.095	0.3	No
Iron ore concentrate	0.300	0.070	8-10	No
Sulfur pyrite	0.100	0.003	8	Yes
Cement	0.090	0.020	-	Yes
Caustic soda ash	0.037	0.007	-	Yes
Lumpy sulfur	3.000	0.100	-	No

< > = Average size of particles in mm; MPS = Maximum particle size in mm.

The main ES criterion of the BDC loading/unloading techniques is the maximum allowable concentration (MAC) of the dust in the air within a working zone. For the most part of the BDC transported by water, the MAC values make 4-6 mg/m³ [2].

In the Table 2, the values are given of the dust MAC excess in the air within a radius of 10 meters from the place of unloading of the grapple bucket with the various BDC [3].

Table 2. Excess of dust MAC in air within radius of 10 m from place of unloading of grapple bucket.

Cargo name	Excess of MAC, time
Coal	7-50
Ore	8-15
Superphosphate	60-150
Potassium chloride	6-50
Lumpy sulfur	20-50
Apatite concentrate	500-700

The intensity of the environment dust pollution depends on the volume and the physical and chemical properties of the BDC reloaded in the ports, the type of the used loading/unloading operations and the technological protection

degree. The most intensive dust formation accompanies the BDC transshipment performed by the open method, versions of which are the grab loading, the direct loading from train to ship-hold, etc.

A violation of technologies, transshipment conditions and maximum permissible emission standards results in an increased air pollution. Also harmful substances settle on the adjacent water area and soil, which jeopardizes human health and leads to a flora and fauna degradation. Often in the towns and villages located close to the large coal terminals, the environmental situation is similar to that in the mining settlements: the coal dust spreads everywhere causing damage to the environment, Figure (1).

Figure 1. Dust formation in vicinity of coal loading/unloading operations.

Source: Pikabu.ru. [4]

As a result of the BDC loading/unloading operations with use of technical means not suitable for working with these kinds of cargos and located within the human settlements adjacent to the terminals, the pollution with harmful substances embraces the atmospheric air, the surrounding water area and soils; so the environmental situation is worsened much, which causes the oncology diseases and the population life expectancy reduction in such settlements.

In the absence of the closed loading/unloading equipment and the warehouses for the BDC storage of the closed type, on one hand, and in the conditions of the increasing turnover of the transported goods, on the other hand, a considerable worsening of the environmental situation can be possible in such settlements causing a social tension and an outflow of residents from there. [5]

It is quite evident that the safety of the reloading operations including the protection against the dust is determined by how perfect is the reloading equipment & the technology of work, how strictly the established requirements for the correct equipment operation are observed, how well trained is the service personnel and how skillfully and correctly the implementation of the loading/unloading operations is running. Failure to comply with these listed requirements leads to emergencies with environmental consequences. That is why keeping in memory and strict implementation of the established norms and rules of the transshipment operations is mandatory in the ports.

The possible measures on the ES improvement on the different stages of the BDC transportation can be listed as follows:

3. On the stage of transshipping operations

On the stage of transshipping operations implementation (loading/unloading).

Providing the transshipping process with the adequate sanitary and hygienic conditions including as follows [6]:

- mechanization and remote control of loading processes, automatic signaling of the progress of individual works and operations related to the probability of the dust emission;

- application of dedusting devices and sanitary-technical installations guaranteeing the high effectiveness of the dusty air cleaning;
- self-locking of the reloading equipment by installed cleaning sanitary devices and dust suppression systems;
- hermetic sealing of the areas of the cargo transportation and transshipment;
- proposals consideration for optimal arrangement of sanitary protection zones and measures of pollution prevention of the coastal waters.

At the crane scheme of mechanization of BDC transshipment, the grapple buckets should be self-sealing; their height of opening over the upper surface of the load (stack) should not exceed 1 m.

It is necessary to store BDC (fine coals and ores, alumina, phosphates, lumpy sulfur, calcium chloride) indoor in such closed warehouses as tents, bunkers, silos, etc. The low-dust cargos can be stored outdoor on grounds equipped with dedusting systems (protective screens, dedusting hydro-spraying machines, equipment for cargo treatment with surfactants, etc.).

Cleaning of stowage spaces, decks, berths and units of reloading equipment should be carried out only after washing off dust and wetting loose cargo.

The air pollution concentration levels in the port area, the working zones and technological facilities of the ship, in the residential area as well as water objects in the areas of the water use should not exceed the established MAC values.

4. Improvement of equipment and technology of transshipment operations including as follows:

4.1 Managerial methods

Managerial methods. The latter should be based on the scientific organization of the entire process of the BDC transshipment operations in the port and contribute to the minimization of the dust formation values at all the stages of the transshipment operations. The following practical measures would be a good practice:

- development of a guiding methodical document regulating the transshipment

process carrying out organization and order; in this regard, the following should be taken into account: availability and condition of a technical and technological support of the works typical for the area of the port location with due consideration of the natural climatic and weather conditions;

- training for the personnel involved in the works carrying out with due attention to the rules and the features of the reloading works performance so that the minimum dust is formed due to the skillful and correct operation of the reloading equipment and technology of its use;
- continuous monitoring of safety of the transshipment operations;
- constant control conducting of the state of the atmosphere dustiness at all the stages of the transshipment operations in the port and in the surrounding area.

4.2. Engineering measures

Engineering measures foreseeing as follows:

- measures on a rational equipment placement and a selection of an optimal technological mode of the loading/unloading operations;
- wetting of the reloaded cargos, dedusting with steams and foams; along with wetting by pure water, it is advisable to conduct the wetting by an aqueous solution with special additives containing surface-active substances for dust binding;
- aspiration and separation of the technological equipment and the places of the intensive dust formation.
- introduction of the water fog guns, Figure (2).

Figure 2. Fog gun. Coal dust suppression equipment purchased at Vanino port.

Source: [7]²

² In the port of Vanino, a dust suppression system designed to operate in the period of freezing temperatures was tested, RIA AmurPRESS was informed in the press service of the enterprise. [7]

The dust suppression system is a snow generator with an integrated pump. The principle of operation of the new equipment is to form a snow curtain using an aerodynamic cone and a powerful fan. Dust suppression occurs due to the creation and directional spraying of a cloud of fine snow, contributing to the deposition of dust particles. [7]

“The installation for the port of Vanino was purchased precisely taking into account the weather conditions of the region and work directly in the winter, when dusting is intensified due to the delivery of dry coal,” said Valery Balakin, General Director of Port Vanino OJSC. [7]

This dust suppression system in the Vanino Commercial Sea Port will significantly reduce dusting in the loading / unloading area. After testing the new equipment and analyzing its effectiveness, the company's specialists decided to purchase four more similar dust suppression systems. The issue of using a snow generator to suppress dust over large areas is currently being worked out. In a matter of minutes, the installation is able to cover an area within a radius of 60 meters with a snow cloud and put a dense screen for dust. [7]

Figure 3. Dust suppression system WLP.

Source: [8]

Figure 4. Dust suppression of all types of soil with polymers.

Source: [9]³

Installation of anti-dust wind screens and dust suppression systems around the production site along its perimeter, Figures (3) and (4).

4.3. Technological measures

Technological measures in the following ways:

- introduction of continuous production technology featured with the manual operations absence;

³ Dust suppression of all types of soil with polymers. The use of polymer emulsion is an environmentally friendly and cheap solution. When the emulsion is dissolved in water and this solution is introduced into the soil, a 100% result is obtained in suppressing dust and eliminating problems associated with wind and rain soil erosion. Polymeric emulsions can be used on all soils and surfaces. [9]

- automation and mechanization of processes known for the dust release;
- rationalization of the technological process and processing of dust-forming materials in their wet state;
- remote control;
- sealing and isolation of dust-forming equipment, vacuum encapsulation of such equipment operation;
- use of local ventilation, suction devices, exhaust ventilation or supply & exhaust ventilation.

5. Urban planning activities

Among the town-planning activities related to the location, construction and operation of the ports, the important place is given to their location in terms of the impact of the future production activities on the environment and the population living close to the port territory.

At the BDC transportation by water, it is advisable to perform the following main measures able to reduce the blowing-out of small fractions from the cargo and thereby cut the dustiness of the environment:

- use of special containers; notably, one of the promising directions in the containerization of the transportation process is use of the soft containers;
- application of sealing materials based on binding materials, for example, latex, bituminous materials, wastes of the pulp & paper industry;
- uniform spraying (through a nozzle) of liquid binding mixtures resulting in the formation of a strong enough protective film 2-5mm thick on the surface of the dust-forming cargo; it is needed that such film is capable to withstand wind and dynamic loads during the movement of the ship; for example, such are the films obtained from wastes of the pulp & paper industry and the oil refining industry: sulfate-lignite, pitch, liquid bard concentrate;
- screening of the dust-forming cargo surface by the highly concentrated suspensions in the form of pastes having sufficient strength and elasticity as well as chemical agents fixing the dust-forming surface; for example:

aqueous solution of technical lignosulfonates (5% wt.) and polyacrylamide (0.2%) with the flow rate 3 l/m; 2% aqueous solution of latex SKS-65GP with the flow rate 5 l/m; 0.2% solution of carbamide resin with the flow rate 5 l/m.

6. Conclusions and proposals

1. Under the environmental safety of the BDC transportation, it is proposed to mean the state of the BDC-transportation ensuring the protection of the environment and the population from the dust at the required regulatory level.

2. On its nature and content, the current BDC transportation technology leading to the environment pollution with the dust is characterized with the imperfection of the used equipment for BDC transportation, the technology of the transshipping works conducting, the accepted application methods and the insufficient use of effective protective measures for the dust spread prevention in the environment.

3. In the list of the possible activities on the BDC transportation ES improvement, it is proposed to include as follows:

- at the stage of transshipment operations (loading/unloading): ensuring of the sanitary and hygienic conditions during the transshipment process; improvement of the equipment and the technology of the transshipment operations (managerial methods, engineering and technological measures); and urban planning activities;
- at the stage of the BDC transportation by water: use of special containers; use of sealing materials for cargos; forming of a protective film on dust-releasing cargo surfaces; screening of the dust-forming cargo surface with highly concentrated suspensions in the form of pastes.

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